

Matrix-Based Surrogate Model of Neutron Transport for Neutron Spectrum Shaping Applications

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803389

ABSTRACT

Accurate and time efficient prediction of neutron spectrum tailoring is essential for the design of new versatile research reactor. Previous work introduced a transmission-matrix approach, where the spectral response of individual material slabs is precomputed using Monte Carlo simulations and subsequently combined through matrix multiplication to obtain the transmitted neutron spectrum for arbitrary inputs. In this work, the method is extended to multi-slab configurations by incorporating neutron backscattering effects through the Redheffer star product formalism. The approach enables stacking of precomputed single-slab transmission and backscatter matrices while fully accounting for inter-slab coupling and multiple reflections.

Transmission and backscatter matrices were generated for carbon slabs using the MCNP code with the ENDF/B-VIII.0 nuclear data library. The results demonstrate that the Redheffer-based stacking method accurately reproduces full Monte Carlo simulations of composite filters, while simple matrix multiplication underestimates neutron moderation for strongly scattering systems. Remaining deviations are primarily attributed to the limited angular discretizations of the matrices. Nevertheless, the achieved accuracy is sufficient for use as a surrogate model within optimization frameworks such as genetic algorithms, where small systematic errors can be compensated during optimization.

The developed formalism represents a significant step toward fast, data-driven design of neutron filters for spectrum tailoring in advanced research reactor applications.

Keywords: Neutron spectrum tailoring, transmission matrices, Redheffer star product, surrogate model

1. INTRODUCTION

Nuclear research reactors remain essential tools for scientific and technological progress across a wide range of fields, extending well beyond nuclear engineering. However, in recent decades, the decommissioning of several research reactors has not been offset by new construction, resulting in a growing shortage of accessible experimental neutron facilities.

To address this gap, the Versatile European Reactor for Neutron Irradiation and Nuclear Research (VERONICA) project [1, 2] has been launched, aiming to develop a new multi-purpose research reactor capable of supporting a broad range of applications. One way to expand the range of possible applications is by enabling flexible neutron spectrum tailoring.

A reactor facility capable of modifying its neutron energy spectrum on demand would significantly enhance its versatility, creating new opportunities in materials testing, fusion research, Small Modular Reactors (SMRs), and Generation IV technologies. Achieving such spectral control requires an efficient methodology to design and optimise neutron filters that transform the source spectrum into a desired output spectrum for specific experiments.

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Existing approaches to neutron spectrum tailoring are typically forward in nature: they compute the resulting neutron flux spectrum for a given beamline or filter configuration [3]. In contrast, our ongoing work explores an inverse approach – starting from a desired target neutron spectrum and determining which filter configuration can produce it. This inverse problem can be efficiently addressed using optimisation algorithms such as genetic algorithms [4]. However, these algorithms require evaluation of a large number of filter configurations, typically on the order of 10^4 or more for each required spectrum. Performing full Monte Carlo neutron transport simulations for every configuration would be computationally prohibitive.

To overcome this limitation, our previous work introduced the concept of transmission matrices [5], building on earlier response-matrix and operator-based formulations of neutron transport [6, 7]. In that formulation, the spectral modification induced by a slab of material is precomputed using Monte Carlo simulations and expressed as a linear operator acting on the incoming neutron spectrum. Once the transmission matrices are available, the outgoing spectrum for any arbitrary input can be obtained rapidly through matrix multiplication, enabling efficient evaluation of candidate filters during optimisation.

This work builds on this foundation and focuses on extending the transmission matrix method to multi-slab configurations. When several slabs are stacked to form a composite filter, simply multiplying the individual transmission matrices is insufficient, as it neglects scattering between different slabs. To correctly describe multiple reflections and internal coupling between layers, the Redheffer star product formalism [8] is employed. In addition, this work investigates the formulation of transmission and backscatter matrices based on neutron current rather than flux, to provide a more accurate physical description of neutron transport.

Section 2 introduces the mathematical framework underlying the current-based formulation and the use of the Redheffer star product for combining slabs. Section 3 describes the computational model used to generate the transmission and backscatter matrices. Section 4 presents the results and discusses the accuracy and limitations of the proposed approach. Finally, Section 5 provides concluding remarks and outlines future steps towards integrating the matrix-based surrogate model into a genetic optimisation framework for neutron spectrum tailoring.

2. MATHEMATICAL MODEL

Our ultimate goal is to create a surrogate model that describes neutron transport through a combination of various slabs in the beam port of a future reactor design. The input quantity is the neutron flux $\phi_{\text{in}}(E)$ in an empty beam port, while the desired output is the outgoing neutron flux $\phi_{\text{out}}(E)$ after the neutron filter. The neutron flux can be represented as a vector, where ϕ_i denotes the flux in energy group E_i . By analogy with other linear transport problems, this can be expressed as

$$\phi_{\text{out}}(E) = \mathbf{T}_\phi \phi_{\text{in}}(E), \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{T}_ϕ is a transmission matrix describing the modification of the neutron flux by the filter.

However, neutron flux is a scalar quantity and does not directly represent the directional flow of neutrons. To introduce directionality and better capture the underlying transport physics, it is more appropriate to work with the neutron current $J(E, \mu)$, where $\mu = \cos \theta$ denotes the cosine of the angle between the neutron direction and the slab normal. The relationship between flux and current can be written as

$$J(E, \mu) = \mathbf{Q} \phi(E, \mu), \quad (2)$$

where \mathbf{Q} is a diagonal matrix containing the discrete angular weights w_a and directional cosines μ_a used

in the angular discretisation, i.e.

$$\mathbf{Q} = \text{diag}(|\mu_a|w_a) \otimes \mathbf{I}_G,$$

with \mathbf{I}_G being the identity matrix in energy space. The total transformation for flux can then be expressed as

$$\phi_{\text{out}}(E, \mu) = \mathbf{Q}^{-1} \mathbf{T} \mathbf{Q} \phi_{\text{in}}(E, \mu), \quad (3)$$

where \mathbf{T} is the transformation matrix operating on current rather than flux.

2.1. Stacking of matrices

Using the established reactor physics notation for partial neutron current J^\pm , where the subscript denotes the current's direction, we can write the response of a single slab as

$$J_{\text{out}}^\pm = \mathbf{T} J_{\text{in}}^\pm \quad J_{\text{out}}^\mp = \mathbf{B} J_{\text{in}}^\pm \quad (4)$$

The essential point is that \mathbf{T} preserves the current direction, whereas \mathbf{B} reverses it.

Let us consider a simple system consisting of two adjacent slabs, labelled 1 and 2. Each slab is characterised by a transmission matrix \mathbf{T}_i , describing the partial neutron current transmitted through the slab, and a backscatter matrix \mathbf{B}_i , describing the partial current reflected back into the incident direction. Assume a forward-directed current J_{in}^+ enters slab 1. The slab then produces

$$J_1^+ = \mathbf{T}_1 J_{\text{in}}^+ \quad J_1^- = \mathbf{B}_1 J_{\text{in}}^+ \quad (5)$$

The transmitted component J_1^+ then enters slab 2, which in turn produces

$$J_2^+ = \mathbf{T}_2 J_1^+ \quad J_2^- = \mathbf{B}_2 J_1^+ \quad (6)$$

The backscattered current J_2^- re-enters slab 1, is reflected again in the forward direction back into slab 2, and so on. Because \mathbf{B}_1 and \mathbf{B}_2 both reverse direction each time, each pair $\mathbf{B}_1 \mathbf{B}_2$ represents one complete internal reflection between the two slabs.

The total forward outgoing current J_{out}^+ through the two-slab system can be written as a series accounting for all possible numbers of back-and-forth reflections:

$$J_{\text{out}}^+ = \left[\mathbf{T}_2 + \mathbf{T}_2 \mathbf{B}_1 \mathbf{B}_2 + \mathbf{T}_2 (\mathbf{B}_1 \mathbf{B}_2)^2 + \dots \right] \mathbf{T}_1 J_{\text{in}}^+ \quad (7)$$

This is a geometric series that can be summed if $\|\mathbf{B}_1 \mathbf{B}_2\| < 1$. This criterion is satisfied if the system is subcritical. The total transmission matrix for both slabs can then be written as:

$$\mathbf{T}_{12} = \mathbf{T}_2 [\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{B}_1 \mathbf{B}_2]^{-1} \mathbf{T}_1 \quad (8)$$

Equation 8 correctly accounts for all multiple reflections between the slabs. In the limit of weak backscattering ($\mathbf{B}_1, \mathbf{B}_2 \approx 0$), the expression simplifies to

$$\mathbf{T}_{12} \approx \mathbf{T}_2 \mathbf{T}_1,$$

which corresponds to simple sequential multiplication of transmission matrices.

A similar derivation can be performed for the total backscatter matrix, yielding

$$\mathbf{B}_{12} = \mathbf{B}_1 + \mathbf{T}_1 \mathbf{B}_2 [\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{B}_1 \mathbf{B}_2]^{-1} \mathbf{T}_1 \quad (9)$$

2.2. Generalisation to multi-slab filters

For filters composed of multiple slabs, it is convenient to describe each slab i with a full system matrix

$$M_i = \begin{pmatrix} B_i^{\text{front}} & T_i^{\text{back}} \\ T_i^{\text{front}} & B_i^{\text{back}} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (10)$$

The block entries correspond to reflection and transmission as viewed from the front and back sides.

When two such systems are connected, their system matrices must be combined in a way that accounts for all neutron scattering between the various slabs. This is done using the Redheffer star product [8], denoted by \star , defined as

$$M_{12} = M_2 \star M_1 = \begin{pmatrix} B_{12}^{\text{front}} & T_{12}^{\text{back}} \\ T_{12}^{\text{front}} & B_{12}^{\text{back}} \end{pmatrix} = \quad (11)$$

$$= \begin{pmatrix} B_1^{\text{front}} + T_1^{\text{back}} B_2^{\text{front}} [I - B_1^{\text{back}} B_2^{\text{front}}]^{-1} T_1^{\text{front}} & T_1^{\text{back}} [I - B_2^{\text{front}} B_1^{\text{back}}]^{-1} T_2^{\text{back}} \\ T_2^{\text{front}} [I - B_1^{\text{back}} B_2^{\text{front}}]^{-1} T_1^{\text{front}} & B_2^{\text{back}} + T_2^{\text{front}} B_1^{\text{back}} [I - B_2^{\text{front}} B_1^{\text{back}}]^{-1} T_2^{\text{back}} \end{pmatrix}.$$

These matrix elements respectively describe the transmission and reflection as viewed from the front and back sides of the combined system.

This formulation enables accurate and efficient modelling of multi-layer neutron filters while preserving all multiple-scattering effects between layers. By recursively applying the Redheffer product, any number of slabs can be combined into a single equivalent system matrix:

$$M_{\text{total}} = M_N \star M_{N-1} \star \cdots \star M_1.$$

This approach enables efficient construction of composite filters from precomputed single-slab transport data, preserving all multiple-scattering effects and avoiding the need for repeated full Monte Carlo simulations.

3. COMPUTATIONAL MODEL

The transmission (T) and backscatter (B) matrices were calculated using the stochastic neutron transport code MCNP [9] with the ENDF/B-VIII.0 nuclear data library [10]. The geometry comprised a $1 \text{ m} \times 1 \text{ m}$ slab in vacuum, with calculations performed for several thicknesses. The slab material was ^{12}C , a commonly used moderator in reactor physics. It was chosen because it exhibits strong scattering and weak absorption, making it a challenging test case for the transmission-matrix approach: accurate modelling requires capturing numerous scattering events with minimal absorption, a regime in which simple matrix multiplication becomes less accurate. It was preferred over hydrogenous materials such as H or H_2O because it provides higher backscattering and smaller energy loss per collision.

The simulated slab thicknesses were chosen based on the mean free path of thermal neutrons ($E = 25 \text{ meV}$) in carbon, defined as $\lambda = \frac{1}{\Sigma_{\text{total}}(E=25 \text{ meV})}$. The calculations covered the range from 1λ to 10λ , ensuring inclusion of both thin and moderately thick scattering regimes.

The neutron source was modelled as a plane with uniform spectral intensity distributed over $G = 640$ logarithmically spaced energy groups, spanning the energy range $E \in [0.1 \text{ meV}, 20 \text{ MeV}]$.

The surface current was tallied using the MCNP F1 tally, which provides the directional neutron current crossing the slab boundaries.

Because the T and B matrices depend on both energy and angle, the source and tallies were discretised into $A = 5$ bins. It should be emphasised that this discretisation was applied only to the source and tally definitions, while the neutron transport itself remained continuous in angle within the Monte Carlo simulation. The angular bin boundaries were defined as

$$\mu_a = \cos \left[\arcsin \left(\frac{a}{A} \right) \right], \quad a = 0, 1, 2, \dots, A, \quad (12)$$

where $\mu = \cos \theta$ denotes the cosine of the polar angle relative to the slab normal. Only the polar dependence (θ) was considered, while the azimuthal angle (ϕ) was integrated over a single bin.

A fine angular resolution is desirable because, during matrix stacking, repeated matrix multiplications effectively average over the angular bins, resulting in a gradual loss of angular detail and, consequently, deviations in the predicted spectrum, particularly at low energies where multiple scattering dominates. Increasing the number of angular bins systematically improves agreement with full Monte Carlo results by reducing this averaging effect. However, excessively fine angular discretisation substantially increases computational cost, making the precomputation of matrices less practical. A compromise of $A = 5$ angular bins was therefore adopted, as this was found to provide sufficient accuracy for a fast surrogate model while keeping the matrix generation time manageable. A more systematic investigation of angular discretisation effects is beyond the scope of this conference contribution and will be addressed in future work.

With this setup, the resulting transmission and backscatter matrices have dimensions

$$(G \cdot A) \times (G \cdot A),$$

representing the coupling between all energy and angular groups for both incident and outgoing neutron currents.

Each matrix element $T_{E_{in}, \mu_{in}, E_{out}, \mu_{out}}$ was normalised to the incident neutron current $J_{E_{in}, \mu_{in}}$ on the entrance surface of the slab, before any neutron–material interaction occurred. This means that every element of the transmission and backscatter matrices represents the probability that a neutron entering the slab in a specific energy and angular bin (E_{in}, μ_{in}) will emerge from the opposite or the same side of the slab into an outgoing bin (E_{out}, μ_{out}). Such normalisation ensures that the matrices are independent of the absolute source intensity and depend solely on the material properties and geometry.

4. RESULTS

This section presents the results of Monte Carlo simulations used to generate single-slab transmission and backscatter matrices, as well as their validation through stacking tests. The objective is to evaluate the capability of the Redheffer star product to reproduce multi-slab neutron transport. For comparison, results obtained using simple transmission-matrix multiplication and full MCNP simulations are also presented.

4.1. Single-slab transmission matrices

Figure 1 shows the structure of a representative transmission matrix for a ^{12}C slab of thickness $d = 1.8 \text{ cm} = 1 \lambda$.

Each element $T_{E_{in}, \mu_{in}, E_{out}, \mu_{out}}$ represents the probability that a neutron entering the slab in a given energy and angular bin will emerge on the opposite surface in another energy and angular bin.

To better visualise the spectral and angular trends, Figure 2 presents the same matrix integrated separately over direction (left) and energy (right).

The energy-integrated form highlights the effects of scattering on the direction of outgoing neutrons. The figure shows the energy-integrated outgoing neutron direction distribution for each incoming an-

Figure 1. Full transmission matrix of a $d = 1.8$ cm thick slab of ^{12}C .

Figure 2. Transmission matrix of a $d = 1.8$ cm = 1λ thick slab of ^{12}C , integrated over directions (left) and over energies (right). The figure notes upper bin bounds.

gular bin, globally normalised to unity. In a thin slab, a large proportion of neutrons pass through without significant change in their original direction distribution (highlighted with a black outline), except for those neutrons that already enter the slab at a significant angle. In a thicker slab, this distribution is significantly more spread over the spatial angle, regardless of the initial direction.

In the angle-integrated form, the physical meaning of the transmission matrix is easily understood. The diagonal elements indicate neutrons that have passed through the material without interacting. Below-diagonal elements correspond mostly to moderated neutrons, with the effects of complete neu-

tron thermalisation beginning to appear at lower incoming energies.

4.2. Matrix stacking validation

The accuracy of the matrix stacking approach was evaluated by comparing three methods of current calculation. The first, J_{MCNP} , is the reference current obtained directly from MCNP calculations of the complete multi-slab system. The second, $J_T = T_N T_{N-1} \dots T_1 J_{in}$, is a simple sequential multiplication of single-slab transmission matrices, neglecting inter-slab scattering. The third, $J_{T+B} = [M_N \star \dots \star M_1]_{(0,1)} J_{in}$, uses the Redheffer star product to construct the full system transmission matrix, fully accounting for multiple reflections between slabs.

Figure 3 compares the resulting outgoing currents for systems composed of two and ten slabs. A uniform current distribution over all energy bins was chosen as the input to validate the method across all energies.

Figure 3. Comparison of neutron current per unit lethargy obtained from the full MCNP calculation (J_{MCNP}) and from matrix-based surrogate models for an incoming current J_{in} , for stacks of two (left) and ten (right) 1λ -thick ^{12}C slabs. The Redheffer result (J_{T+B}) accounts for inter-slab scattering, while the transmission-only result (J_T) neglects backward-propagating currents between slabs.

For the two-slab case, both the simple matrix multiplication and the Redheffer star-product approaches agree closely with the reference MCNP results, indicating that inter-slab scattering plays a minor role in thin configurations. However, as the number of slabs increases, the difference between the two approaches becomes more pronounced. For $N = 10$, the simple multiplication method J_T significantly underestimates the degree of moderation. This behaviour arises because simple stacking accounts only for neutrons that travel directly forward through each slab, neglecting those that undergo backward scattering between adjacent layers. Since the forward-moving neutrons are typically of higher energy, owing to their longer mean free paths, the resulting spectrum appears harder than the true one.

In contrast, the Redheffer-based current J_{T+B} , which correctly incorporates inter-slab scattering, reproduces the MCNP reference spectrum J_{MCNP} far more accurately. Some deviation between the two remain, primarily due to the finite angular discretisation of the matrices. In the matrix formalism, the neutron current within each angular bin is effectively averaged after each slab. Increasing the number of angular bins would reduce this averaging effect and improve agreement, but at the cost of substantially higher computational effort. Given the intended use of the matrices as a surrogate model within a genetic algorithm, this residual deviation is acceptable: it remains small enough to be compensated by the adaptive nature of the optimisation process, while preserving the computational efficiency that motivates the approach.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This work extends the transmission-matrix approach for neutron spectrum tailoring to multi-slab configurations by incorporating inter-slab scattering using the Redheffer star product. Transmission and backscatter matrices for carbon slabs were generated with MCNP and validated against full Monte Carlo calculations. The results show that the Redheffer stacking method reproduces neutron transfer through layered systems significantly better than simple matrix multiplication, which underestimates neutron moderation in strongly scattering slabs. This improvement arises from the correct treatment of backscattering between slabs, which is essential for accurately describing neutron moderation.

Some deviations from the reference results remain, mainly due to the finite angular discretisation of the transmission matrices. Averaging the neutron current within angular bins introduces minor discrepancies, particularly at low energies. However, the achieved level of agreement is sufficient for use as a surrogate model in genetic algorithms. The reduction in computational cost outweighs the residual inaccuracy, as such optimisation frameworks can adaptively compensate for small systematic differences.

Overall, the presented methodology provides a robust foundation for fast, matrix-based neutron transport modelling. Future work will focus on integrating the approach into a complete optimisation framework for automated neutron filter design and spectrum tailoring.

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